

Annex: 3

SOCIAL INTERVENTIONS

Landscape of psychological and social interventions for anxiety, depression and psychosis and recommendations for investment to advance the field.

June 2025

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ASSERTIVE COMMUNITY TREATMENT (ACT)

Pipeline stage: Improve and test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Researcher and provider of training, consultation, and evaluation services in support of ACT, USA
- Clinical and Research Psychiatrist, Early intervention Psychosis Service. Malawi and UK

Target disorders:

ACT targets severe and persistent mental illnesses including schizophrenia, bipolar disorder and severe depression. It also targets co-occurring substance use disorders.

Overview of intervention:

ACT is an evidence-based, community-centred model designed to support individuals with severe mental illnesses who face challenges in independent living, accessing traditional healthcare, and managing symptoms. Unlike standard clinic-based care, ACT aims to deliver personalised, holistic services directly within clients' living and working environments (SAMHSA, 2008). It involves a multidisciplinary team providing comprehensive, individualised services, including mental health treatment, medication management, and support for needs like housing and employment directly in people's homes and community settings, generally on a 24/7 basis.

ACT utilises multidisciplinary teams to provide a broad spectrum of services, including mental health treatment (e.g., symptom management, medication, and psychotherapy), integrated dual disorder treatment for co-occurring mental health and substance use issues, family support and psychoeducation, and vocational assistance to enhance employment outcomes. The model also emphasises community integration and peer support, fostering social inclusion and leveraging lived experience. A key feature of ACT is its assertive outreach, ensuring consistent engagement with individuals who may be reluctant to access conventional services or receive treatment (Bond & Drake, 2015).

Scope:

ACT has been implemented with multiple variations across diverse contexts globally. This review provides an overview of the evidence supporting ACT, with an emphasis on the key elements that may be critical for the approach to be scaled. Given the lack of progression of ACT to widespread adoption despite its use for over 5 decades, it also examines key obstacles to this.

Intervention development and theory of change:

ACT is a mental health care model – dating from the 1970s - designed to overcome the limitations of traditional approaches by delivering services directly within the community. Historically, mental health care relied on brief hospitalisations for stabilisation, followed by inadequate community support, leading to frequent relapses and a "revolving door" of readmissions. ACT disrupts this cycle by providing continuous, proactive, and comprehensive care in real-world settings, aiming to reduce hospitalisations and promote community integration. Emerging from the recognition of systemic failures in treating individuals with severe mental illnesses, ACT shifts the focus from labelling patients as "noncompliant" to addressing systemic gaps in care (Bond & Drake, 2015).

ACT operates through a multidisciplinary, team-based model where professionals collaboratively tailor services to meet each client's unique needs. Unlike traditional models that rely on fragmented service coordination, ACT delivers mental health treatment, crisis intervention, and practical support as part of an integrated, individualised plan. Services are provided in vivo—directly in the community—ensuring real-time adjustments, consistent monitoring, and fostering higher client engagement and satisfaction. With 24/7 availability, ACT seeks to enhance stability, continuity, and trust, supporting individuals as active members of the community (Bond & Drake, 2015).

Key components of ACT include (van Veldhuizen, 2007; Tempier et al., 2012; Botha et al., 2014):

- Multidisciplinary Teams: ACT teams consist of case managers, psychiatrists, psychologists, and substance abuse counsellors who collaborate to provide coordinated, evidence-based care and recovery-oriented rehabilitation.
- Assertive Outreach: ACT engages individuals in their homes or community settings rather than relying solely on clinical environments, ensuring continuous care and improving patient engagement.
- Shared Caseloads and 24-Hour Coverage: Teams work with shared caseloads, ensuring 24-hour service availability and acting as gatekeepers to psychiatric wards, providing continuous support and crisis intervention.
- Individualised Support and Recovery-Oriented Rehabilitation: ACT tailors treatment to each individual's needs, addressing medical, psychological, and social aspects of recovery. Services include symptom management, medication, psychotherapy, integrated dual diagnosis (alcohol and substance use) treatment, and vocational support.
- Social Support and Community Integration: ACT emphasises rebuilding and maintaining relationships with family, friends, and the community. Studies suggest ACT interventions increase the number of significant social relationships in a patient's network, contributing to long-term recovery and inclusion.

Several key elements are believed to contribute to its success. Proactive engagement ensures continuous support, as ACT teams actively work with patients in their homes and communities, fostering trust beyond traditional clinical settings (Bond et al., 2001). Individualised treatment addresses diverse needs, including medication, housing, finances, employment, education, and relationships. Families receive guidance to strengthen social networks and reduce hostility toward loved ones with schizophrenia. Additionally, collaboration with local services, police, and general practitioners enhances community integration, ensuring comprehensive, coordinated care (Bond et al., 2001; Tempier et al., 2012).

ACT has been adapted to serve diverse populations and settings. Flexible ACT (FACT) is a Dutch adaptation that integrates ACT services within clinical case management teams, allowing individualised support for stable patients while maintaining assertive outreach for those at risk of relapse. This model is particularly useful in rural areas where fully staffed multidisciplinary teams may not be feasible. Forensic ACT tailors services for individuals involved in the criminal justice system, collaborating with justice agencies to support jail diversion efforts and incorporating supervised residential programmes and probation officers into treatment teams. Youth ACT extends the model to young adults experiencing recent onset schizophrenia, ensuring early and specialised intervention. Additionally, ACT continues to evolve by integrating evidence-based practices such as Integrated Dual Diagnosis Treatment, family psychoeducation, supported employment, and Illness Management and Recovery, enhancing its effectiveness in addressing co-occurring conditions and promoting long-term recovery (Bond et al., 2001; Bond et al., 2009; Tempier et al., 2012; Goscha et al., 2022).

An interviewee explained that one of the earliest contributions of this approach was the development of an integrated care team, where professionals from different disciplines collaborate closely to support

individuals needing ACT, particularly those with schizophrenia and significant functional challenges. This model ensures continuous care coordination, unlike fragmented services from multiple providers. Another key contribution was bringing services directly to individuals, which is crucial for those who struggle with generalising learning from across multiple different environments. Additionally, ACT services were designed to be both intensive and flexible, maintaining small caseloads—typically no more than 120 individuals for a team of 10 to 12 staff (SAMHSA, 2008). Some individuals may receive ACT-level care for 10 to 15 years, with support ranging from multiple daily visits to less frequent engagement. This adaptability potentially allows the team to meet each person’s specific needs effectively.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

ACT has been highly effective for individuals with severe mental illness in addressing both symptomology and factors such as homelessness. Most recently, a systematic review by Sánchez-Balsa and Sobrido-Prieto (2023) of 13 studies found that ACT significantly improved outcomes for individuals with schizophrenia, leading to a 44.0-point increase in symptomatic remission (on the 210 point Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale, PANSS) and a lower hospital readmission rate (19.1% vs. 39.9% in controls). Compared to Community-Based Rehabilitation (CBR), ACT was more effective in reducing relapses and enhancing social participation due to its assertive, individualised approach.

Coldwell and Bender’s (2007) meta-analysis of 10 studies (5,775 subjects) further supports ACT’s efficacy, particularly for homeless individuals with severe mental illness. ACT reduced homelessness by 37% and improved psychiatric symptoms by 26% in randomised trials, with observational studies showing even greater reductions (104% in homelessness, 62% in symptom severity). However, its impact on hospitalisation rates was inconsistent. These findings highlight ACT’s effectiveness in improving symptomatic and social outcomes for individuals with severe mental illness.

Reports of safety concerns regarding ACT are few and are linked to broader mental health service standards. For example, reference to safety in recent NHS England guidance on the use of ACT emphasises the importance of not using ‘Did Not Attend’ as a basis for termination of an intervention programme (NHS, 2025).

Relevance to PLE:

An interviewee noted that during the initial development of the ACT model, there was little involvement of people with lived experience (PLE). However, as the peer movement grew, efforts have been made to integrate trained PLE into multidisciplinary teams. According to the interviewee, this integration has improved significantly over time and contributed to a broader recovery movement within ACT. The model has since evolved to emphasise person-centred care, focusing not only on preventing hospitalisation but also on helping individuals achieve meaningful personal goals, such as employment, relationships, and stable housing. The interviewee suggested that the inclusion of PLE has brought a valuable perspective, strengthening ACT’s recovery-oriented approach, although it was noted that the Tool for Measurement of Assertive Community Treatment (TMACT) does not specify a role for PLE in its assessment of intervention fidelity.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

ACT operates through a multidisciplinary team—including nurses, psychiatrists, vocational specialists, and substance abuse specialists—that delivers direct services rather than referring persons to other provision. While this model is effective, its implementation in rural areas presents challenges due to workforce shortages, lower population density, and limited resources. As a result, rural ACT teams tend to be smaller

and less specialised, requiring staff to take on broader roles. However, these adaptations can also bring benefits, such as reduced isolation and increased peer support for staff (Meyer & Morrissey, 2007).

A core strength of ACT is its emphasis on assertive outreach, which brings care directly to patients and reduces travel burdens. This is particularly valuable in rural settings, where geographic barriers can otherwise limit access to consistent care. In cases where full ACT implementation is not feasible, intensive case management may offer a more adaptable alternative by coordinating rather than directly providing services (Meyer & Morrissey, 2007).

Funding mechanisms for ACT vary widely. One interviewee observed that in the USA, for example, there is ongoing debate about the most effective way to provide financing. They noted that the widely adopted fee-for-service - which ties payment to specific services rather than overall care quality – is one of the least effective models. This approach can lead providers to avoid enrolling individuals with severe psychiatric conditions who are difficult to locate or engage, as reimbursement is linked to service frequency. As a result, financial structures directly influence both who receives ACT services and how teams operate.

Service models and resource availability also influence caseloads. Intensive case management generally maintains a low staff-to-consumer ratio, with one staff member serving up to 15 consumers (Meyer & Morrissey, 2007). In the Netherlands, Flexible Assertive Community Treatment (FACT) teams adjust caseloads based on consumer needs, with case managers overseeing up to 20 patients (van Veldhuizen, 2007). These flexible approaches help ensure that ACT remains effective in rural areas by allowing smaller teams to coordinate services and adjust caseloads to balance cost-effectiveness with essential care access (Meyer & Morrissey, 2007).

Despite concerns about cost, it is argued ACT can still be a financially viable option, even in under-resourced settings. Modified assertive interventions have been shown to reduce hospital readmissions and inpatient care days, offsetting the expenses associated with standard ACT implementation. While ACT is often viewed as expensive, its costs may be justified when compared to the higher financial burden of inpatient treatment. By tailoring services to specific needs, it is suggested ACT can remain both affordable and practical, particularly in developing countries where comprehensive care services are limited (Botha et al., 2014).

Interviewees concurred that ACT is an expensive intervention if done well. In a low-resource setting there are severe challenges in mobilising community mental health support for persons with long-term mental disorders, and the multi-disciplinary responsive service envisioned by ACT may not be feasible. However, when proposed for implementation in a high-resource setting, the key can be demonstrating how it ultimately saves money within the broader system. For example, homelessness itself is costly, as individuals without stable housing often rely on expensive emergency services, such as crisis interventions or encounters with the criminal justice system for minor offences. According to one interviewee, the focus should be on showcasing the long-term benefits of ACT. Effective ACT teams not only provide support but also help individuals gain employment. For instance, if a person receiving disability benefits secures a job, their reliance on government assistance decreases, allowing them to contribute financially instead. This shift illustrates how investing in ACT can reduce costs in other areas while improving individuals' independence, stability and quality of life.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Botha et al. (2014) conducted a randomised controlled trial examining the implementation of ACT in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Their findings indicate that modified assertive interventions can effectively reduce hospital readmissions and inpatient stays, particularly in settings where standard care services are limited. Adaptations of ACT have been successfully implemented in countries such as India,

Chile, and China, demonstrating their affordability and feasibility within resource-constrained environments. For instance, a home-based programme in Somalia incorporating psychoeducation, relapse prevention, and family support proved both cost-effective and practical. Additionally, modified ACT models with larger caseloads and less frequent visits have successfully reduced inpatient service use among high-frequency patients. These adaptations show that ACT can be integrated into existing healthcare systems and scaled up to meet community needs without being restricted to a small subset of patients.

Despite these successes, significant challenges remain in implementing ACT in LMICs. Many developing countries face severe resource constraints, including limited funding, inadequate mental health infrastructure, and a shortage of trained professionals. In Africa, only 56.5% of countries offer community-based mental health services, and just 50% have formal mental health policies. Research on ACT in these settings is often limited by small sample sizes due to financial and human resource shortages, making it difficult to achieve balanced study groups and necessitating larger-scale studies for more reliable findings. Additionally, the standard caseloads managed by ACT teams in high-income countries are not sustainable within the overburdened and underfunded healthcare systems of LMICs. Addressing these challenges requires context-specific modifications and greater investment in mental health services to ensure ACT's long-term viability in resource-limited settings (Botha et al., 2014).

The effectiveness of ACT can also vary depending on the context. In the UK large-scale evaluations found no significant advantage for ACT over standard services, likely because standard mental health services had already integrated many practices (e.g. regarding multi-disciplinarity and rapid response) associated with ACT. Similarly, recent controlled trials in the U.S. have produced inconsistent results, possibly due to overall reductions in hospitalisation rates and lengths of stay due to wider policy changes. (Bond & Drake, 2015).

Another challenge lies in the variation in how ACT is implemented across different countries. One interviewee noted that while ACT has been introduced in multiple countries, the extent to which the original model is followed varies. In Norway, for example, fidelity evaluations ensure adherence to all four core components of the model. However, in other regions, fundamental aspects of ACT have been altered. One significant modification is the replacement of ACT's fully dedicated team structure with a more flexible approach, where professionals from different services, such as therapists and employment specialists, collaborate instead. The impact of these changes on ACT's effectiveness remains unclear due to a lack of published research.

Workforce availability also plays a critical role in ACT implementation. One interviewee pointed out that Canada can more easily integrate occupational therapists into ACT teams, whereas U.S. regulations pose challenges in doing so. In Europe, the higher prevalence of psychologists allows them to take on larger roles in ACT teams. These differences underscore the importance of routine fidelity assessments to track how adaptations impact care quality. Additionally, past modifications—such as Forensic ACT for individuals in the justice system and Youth ACT for young people aged 16 to 25—have required substantial changes to service delivery. A newer adaptation, the Child ACT model, aims to support younger populations with serious emotional challenges. However, the interviewee emphasised that while ACT is an established evidence-based practice, many of these adaptations have not undergone rigorous evaluation. This raises concerns about whether they align with ACT principles or represent entirely new interventions that should be studied separately.

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An interviewee with experience of both high- and low-resource settings noted that mental health services in the LMIC in which she currently worked remain largely institution-based, receiving the majority of government funding. In contrast, community-based services are funded at the district level. To address

this, the ACT model has been adapted to fit their local context, aiming to reduce the duration of untreated psychosis by utilising health surveillance assistants stationed at the village level. These team members are required to have completed high school and undergo a two-week training programme. Through ongoing training and experience, they seek to strengthen the primary healthcare system. Given that individuals in this context often go long periods without receiving any treatment, their approach prioritises providing a two-week course of treatment. From a sustainability and feasibility perspective, training non-specialist healthcare workers is more practical than relying on highly trained specialists, which would be too costly. As a result, the traditional ACT model is not well-suited to the setting. Instead, community-based approaches are seen as more viable and aligned with the country's healthcare needs.

Despite the variations in implementation and the challenges faced in low-resource settings, ACT and its adaptations continue to demonstrate potential in improving mental health care in LMICs. The success of modified models in reducing hospitalisations, integrating community support, and utilising non-specialist workers highlights the feasibility of ACT-based approaches in resource-constrained environments. However, ongoing research is needed to assess the long-term effectiveness of these adaptations and ensure they remain consistent with ACT principles. Moving forward, increased investment in mental health infrastructure, workforce training, and policy development will be essential for scaling up community-based interventions and making mental health services more accessible and sustainable globally.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

An interviewee described several challenges ACT faces when serving populations with specific needs or diverse sociodemographic characteristics. One key challenge is ensuring appropriate care for individuals with unique requirements. For example, when a patient is legally blind, the ACT core team must coordinate with external services, as they may lack the necessary expertise themselves.

Language barriers also pose significant difficulties. Some individuals who could greatly benefit from ACT services may not speak the majority language fluently, yet the team may not include members who speak the relevant minority language. To address this, the interviewee has observed creative solutions, such as integrating interpreters into the team to facilitate communication and improve care delivery.

Another concern is the role of social stigma in ACT service provision. Although no published research exists on the topic, the interviewee's team has observed a disproportionate representation of people of colour receiving ACT services. They noted that individuals from these communities with severe mental health conditions may be more likely to be perceived as erratic, unpredictable, or aggressive during assessments. As a result, they are disproportionately referred to the most intensive level of care. These observations suggest potential systemic biases in mental health referrals and highlight the need for further research and awareness to ensure equitable access to appropriate care.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention development and overview of lessons learned:

A key challenge in implementing ACT effectively is maintaining fidelity to the model, which requires substantial financial investment. As one interviewee explained, ACT must be implemented as closely as possible to its original design to achieve its intended outcomes. However, they noted that many programmes in the United States claim to offer ACT but operate with low fidelity due to funding constraints. Historically, ACT's financial justification was based on its ability to reduce costly hospitalisations. However, as long-term psychiatric hospital beds have declined, cost-saving arguments have shifted toward preventing incarceration, homelessness, and excessive use of crisis services. This shift has made making the case for the financial investment required to establish ACT teams more difficult, and not only in the USA.

Another challenge is the lack of a broader service system offering varying levels of care. Without appropriate alternative services, individuals who do not require ACT's intensive support may still be referred to these teams. For example, some may only need occasional community assistance or help attending medical appointments, but in the absence of other options, they are placed in ACT programmes. This misallocation dilutes the model, diverting resources from those who need ACT's high-intensity, wraparound services.

In many contexts the population served by ACT has also changed over time. In the 1990s, ACT primarily supported individuals transitioning from long-term psychiatric hospitalisation. Today, with fewer psychiatric hospitals, ACT teams more often serve individuals with severe substance use disorders, housing instability, and frequent interactions with the criminal justice system. Additionally, more referrals now involve individuals with aggressive behaviours, creating new challenges for staff safety and service delivery.

Looking ahead, there are growing concerns about ACT's sustainability. While mental health needs are rising, the behavioural health workforce is shrinking, raising questions about how ACT teams will continue to function effectively. Future research should examine whether these challenges are consistent across different countries and explore strategies for maintaining high-fidelity ACT models despite workforce and financial constraints.

Overall, while ACT has demonstrated significant success in reducing hospitalizations, enhancing patient engagement, and improving long-term outcomes, major challenges remain. High-intensity care requires substantial resources, making full implementation difficult in areas with limited funding or workforce shortages. Additionally, balancing individualised support with caseload limitations can be challenging, particularly when demand exceeds capacity. However, adaptations such as FACT and forensic ACT illustrate how the model can be tailored to different contexts, ensuring accessibility while maintaining core principles. However, there are risks with adaptations of the model; as Meyer and Morrisey (2007) note "The assertive community treatment label has been disseminated much more rapidly than has its faithful practice". Moving forward, continued investment in training, policy support, and research will be critical for clarifying ACT's sustained impact as a foundational model in mental health care. Key research gaps are focused in these areas and elaborated in the next section.

Recommendations for investment:

It is apparent that over five decades ACT has provided a means of structuring mental health services to be both more responsive and comprehensive in addressing the needs of persons with severe and persistent mental health conditions. It has been particularly effective in reducing rates of re-hospitalisation in settings where 'revolving door' re-admissions were commonplace. However, the intervention remains classified as 'Improve and Test' given the trend for revision of the model to address the numerous challenges restricting adoption at scale. In high-income settings the configuration of mental health services has evolved such that re-hospitalisation is no longer the major risk that it once posed, and the rationale for the intervention has thus had to evolve. In low-income settings, the ACT principles of multi-disciplinarity, assertive outreach, 24-hour coverage, individualised care and social support are of clear relevance, but their operationalisation will often be severely constrained.

In evaluating the potential for ACT to serve as a basis for wider scaling of effective mental health provision in the future the following are thus **key research questions**:

- **Informing strategies to enable ACT implementation with fidelity across diverse settings.** The evidence-base suggests significant benefits for ACT delivered with fidelity as defined by measures such as the Tool for Measurement of Assertive Community Treatment (TMACT) . What strategies

are effective and feasible in enabling implementation of ACT with due fidelity across diverse settings, noting the reported challenges faced in rural settings, diverse funding models and service configuration?

- **Evaluating long-term effectiveness of ACT adaptations.** Where fidelity to the ACT model cannot be achieved, the utility and effectiveness of adaptations (seeking greater flexibility than specified in measures such as TMACT) needs to be more fully documented. What is the long-term effectiveness of these ACT adaptations, and do these adaptations remain sufficiently aligned with original ACT principles in terms of impact on key outcomes?
- **Identification of elements of ACT implementable in low-resource settings.** The significant resource requirements of ACT are well documented. Even adaptations of ACT (such as FACT) are likely to prove difficult to implement in many low-resource contexts. Are there feasible ways of implementing some principles of person-focused ACT in LMICs and other resource-poor environments? How effective are such interventions, and what is the potential for their wider adoption?

Given the significant needs of persons with severe mental illness in terms of prompt receipt of services, the promise of ACT in facilitating this but the multiple challenges in its implementation another form of investment would be a **global consultation on feasible and effective means of mental health outreach services in the context of resource constraints and escalating mental health needs**. This would convene leading researchers and policymakers to take stock of lessons learned from decades of deployment of ACT-informed services and what principles and practices drawn from this experience can be feasibly taken forward in addressing the needs of persons presenting with severe and persistent mental illnesses with current levels of resource availability.

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CASH TRANSFERS

Pipeline stage: Ideate

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Researcher involved in private and public research in Brazil, focused on social protection programming generally [by email exchange].
- Professor and research lead, working at the intersection of mental health and cash transfer programming across Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America.
- Advocate and policy-maker active in mental health programming for high-income countries, including commissioner of research into cash transfer programme adoption.

We additionally contacted major funders and drew on insights provided by these in emails and written documentation shared with us.

Target disorders:

Evidence predominantly focuses on poverty reduction, but as this directly impacts on likelihood of developing and exacerbating depression, anxiety and psychosis, the intervention has applicability for all target conditions.

Overview of intervention:

The evidence-base on cash transfers for influencing mental health outcomes is in its infancy; hence the intervention is positioned at the Ideation stage. Cash transfer programmes are predominantly designed to alleviate poverty by providing direct financial assistance to individuals or households. They can be either unconditional, offering cash without specific requirements (including via universal basic income), or conditional, providing funds contingent on meeting criteria such as ensuring children attend school (Bastagli et al., 2016). In practice, programme designs and mechanisms of action are highly heterogeneous and targeted predominantly at poverty alleviation. However, cash transfers can also be used to incentivise persons to adopt positive behaviours (e.g. adherence to medications, treatment or stopping substance use).

Scope:

Cash transfer programmes are often compared to in-kind supports (e.g. of direct food aid or food banks). The latter supports are not in scope for this deep dive, however, where relevant we draw comparisons to such programmes. This review focuses on general relevance of cash transfers in addressing depression, anxiety and psychosis.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Cash transfers were initially developed in the 2000s and have been globally adopted as a poverty alleviation instrument (see Timeline below).

Cash transfers generally take one of two forms and influence mental health outcomes by acting on the social determinants of mental health.

1. **Unconditional:** Payments can be targeted to specific individuals, families, communities or even populations – usually those living in poverty or experiencing severe health problems. Payments are made without any condition being imposed on recipients. Improved financial stability facilitates better access to healthcare, education, and other services, which are linked to improved mental health outcomes (Fiszbein et al., 2009).
2. **Conditional:** This approach is still targeted towards specific groups, but ties financial support to specific conditions being met, such as regular school attendance or health check-ups, or other behaviours (e.g. attendance in community programmes or initiatives). Programmes in Latin America, for instance, have shown positive impacts on education and health indicators using this approach (Bastagli, 2009). Conditions related to risk factors specific to mental health may also be imposed in so called contingency management interventions which offer rewards for positive actions – e.g. stopping cannabis use (Sheridan Rains et al., 2019).

Lund et al. (2011) identifies two main pathways of action by which cash transfers influence mental health outcomes. First, via the *social causation pathway*, poverty directly affects all health determinants and is associated with poor living conditions, food insecurity, exposure to stress, trauma and violence. All these are risk factors for developing or exacerbating mental health conditions. Second, the *social drift pathway* suggests that persons with mental illness are at increased risk of finding themselves living in poverty; this may be due to stigma and exclusion, inability to work and gain income, high expenditure on health care and potential substance use, or limited social and family resources.

Related theories are elaborated by Jaffee et al. (2024), who discuss cash transfers in the context of *family investment theory* and *family strain theory*.

- **Family Investment Theory** suggests that cash transfers enhance material resources at the family or individual level, directly reducing stress and enabling individuals to build stronger social connections within their families or communities.

- **Family Strain Theory**, highlights how cash transfers alleviate financial precarity, reducing stress associated with housing and food insecurity.

Facilitators of cash transfers being widely adopted as poverty alleviation mechanisms include high level political will and support (e.g. driving programme expansion in Latin America), donor support (e.g. as facilitated by the World Bank in Sub-Saharan Africa) and early evidence of effectiveness. Contextual factors can also act as facilitators e.g. widespread poverty in Latin America in the 1990s and COVID-19 were windows of opportunity for the intervention being widely adopted. Weak administrative and banking systems are a critical barrier that have hindered scaling and adoption particularly in low-resource settings in Africa. Limited national financial capacity is a further barrier to programme expansion, making adoption of universal basic income unfeasible.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Cash transfer programmes have been primarily implemented to support economically vulnerable populations, such as individuals living in poverty or financial instability, those in humanitarian contexts, and children or adolescents from vulnerable families. While these programmes have not been explicitly studied in populations solely affected by depression, anxiety or psychosis, individuals with these conditions are more likely to live in poverty and have thus been included incidentally in the programmes and broader studies.

The evidence base on cash transfer programmes predominantly stems from two types of studies:

1. **Pilot Programme Evaluations:** Many studies have used randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and quasi-experimental designs to evaluate pilot programmes under highly controlled conditions. These studies often involve significant implementation support from agencies (e.g., the World Bank or national governments) and research institutions. However, such high levels of support are often unsustainable when programmes are scaled nationally and may result in overly positive effects.
2. **Scaled Programme Effectiveness:** Other studies focus on assessing the effectiveness of cash transfer programmes at scale using routine data or large cross-sectional surveys over time. These studies often face critique regarding their inability to appropriately control for bias and the lack of robust control groups. Cash transfer programmes frequently evolve over the course of their implementation, for example adjusting payments to inflation and/or potentially expanding to include other support mechanisms (e.g. attendance at support groups). The changing nature of cash transfer programmes thus further complicates attribution of effect to specific design features.

Several systematic reviews have assessed the impact of cash transfers on mental health outcomes, showing a general trend toward positive, though variable, effects; in rare cases, harms have also been reported. The fact that programmes focus on economically vulnerable groups further limits the generalizability of findings regarding the effectiveness of cash transfer programmes to other populations.

The evidence base generally relates to specific populations, settings or age groups, as such key findings from prominent reviews are included below:

- **Brydon et al (2024)** synthesized evidence from 164 studies in 14 high-income countries (predominantly the USA), focusing on child/family-focused cash transfers or income support for low-wage workers. Of 48 studies on mental health outcomes, 32 reported positive effects, 10 showed inconsistent results, and 6 highlighted potential harm (e.g. where cash transfers conversely enabled substance use). Improved food security was identified as the primary mechanism driving positive impacts.

- **Zimmerman et al. (2020)** reviewed cash transfer programmes targeting young people (ages 11–22) in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), synthesising evidence from studies of 43,861 participants across nations such as Mexico, Kenya, Uganda, and South Africa. The majority of interventions (spanning one to ten years in duration) were unconditional. While reductions in depressive and anxiety symptoms or biological markers (e.g., cortisol) were noted, the pooled effect size on depressive symptoms was non-significant (Cohen’s $d = 0.02$, 95% CI: -0.19 to 0.23 ; $p=.85$). The review flagged high heterogeneity and moderate-to-high risk of bias.
- **Wollburg et al. (2023)** extended **Zimmerman’s (2020)** analysis to include young people and adults, examining 13 programmes in 17 studies (26,794 participants) predominantly conducted in sub-Saharan Africa. The majority of programmes were unconditional and targeted rural populations facing poverty or health risks (e.g. HIV). A meta-analysis (11 studies, 22,488 participants) showed significant improvements in depressive and anxiety symptoms post-intervention (moderate-certainty evidence) either during the programme or immediately post cessation. However, effects did not persist in follow-up periods (2-9 years after financial support stopped). This evidence is of low certainty due to limited sample sizes, attrition, and participant mobility. No adverse effects were reported.
- **Van Daalen (2022)** and **Jeong & Trako (2022)** examined the effectiveness of cash transfers in humanitarian contexts. Findings were mixed: Van Daalen observed that while some programmes reduced depressive symptoms, irregular payments or abrupt termination of cash support heightened distress. Jeong and Trako highlighted strong evidence of financial and asset-based benefits, but they found health-related outcomes were rarely assessed. Both reviews underscored the need for better disaggregated analyses by sex/gender and more robust longitudinal studies.

Research on cash transfer programmes has largely focused on demonstrating the high potential, rather than actual effect, on mental health outcomes. Hence, significant research gaps remain:

Limited Research on Specific Mental Health Conditions: There is a notable lack of studies explicitly targeting individuals with depression, anxiety, or psychosis. Existing research often lacks sufficient statistical power to draw robust conclusions for these groups, leading to potential overestimation of effects. Further, there are challenges with fully identifying the causal mechanisms behind how cash transfers affect mental health outcomes – current studies largely use self-administered tools to assess outcomes but do not test mechanisms of action.

1. **Uncertainty Around Programme Design, Context and Longevity of Diverse Effects:** Key questions remain unanswered regarding how programme design features (e.g., conditional vs. unconditional transfers, magnitude of transfers (absolute and relative), mechanisms of transfer etc.) and the duration of implementation influence mental health outcomes. For example, evidence on whether programmes are better off making one lump sum transfer vs. regular transfers of cash is conflicting. Additionally, the persistence of effects post programme cessation is unclear. Studies also struggle to comprehensively consider and assess how contextual socio-economic and political features influence effectiveness, social cohesion and equity. For example, Fotta and Schmidt (2022) point to the fact that cash transfers are often introduced in times of social service reduction (including for health) and that agencies administering cash transfers gain huge power over local populations and resources. This is the case particularly in low-income countries where state mechanisms for cash transfer administration may be ineffective. Clinical effectiveness is thus critically also dependent on other concurrent initiatives and must be considered in light of these.

- 2. Need for Comparative Effectiveness Research:** There is a scarcity of studies comparing the relative effectiveness of cash transfers to other interventions (as well as cost-effectiveness – see next sections). For example, Haushofer et al. (2020) conducted a study in Kenya that compared cash transfers, Problem Management Plus (PM+) and a combination of both interventions against a control group. Interestingly, cash transfers alone were as effective, if not more so, than the combination of cash transfers with PM+, while PM+ alone appeared ineffective. This highlights the need for further research into how cash transfers perform relative to alternative approaches.

Relevance to PLE:

There is considerable evidence available regarding the lived experience of persons accessing cash transfers. People with lived experiences of poverty often view cash transfers, whether conditional or unconditional, as essential yet complex interventions. They recognise these programmes as necessary for addressing immediate needs but often criticise their limited scope in addressing long-term challenges, such as achieving broader well-being or behavioural changes (Yoshino et al, 2023; Zizumbo-Colunga, 2023). For example, in contexts like Mexico, cash transfer programmes have been shown to exacerbate social tensions, with recipients vulnerable to stigma, conflict, and even violence due to unequal access to resources or perceived favouritism (Zizumbo-Colunga, 2023; Bertoluzza et al., 2024). However, such programmes can also provide direct psychological benefits, including feelings of empowerment and hope for a better future, especially when paired with supportive interventions like counselling (Yoshino et al, 2023; Bertoluzza et al., 2024).

Appropriate intervention design is therefore important when considering cash transfers and effects on mental health outcomes. For example, it is essential that programmes consider how finances are made available, and whether processes used for this result in stigmatisation or additional distress. Gaps in research around subjective experiences of access to the intervention and how these in turn impact effectiveness have been identified by interviewees involved in offering policy advice.

People living in poverty have often been involved in the design of pilot programmes to advise on issues such as frequency and magnitude of payment. However, there is no account of persons with lived experience of mental health conditions specifically being involved in cash transfer design. Potential barriers to involvement include bias among programme funders/designers believing that PLE may “game” the system by exaggerating needs and prioritisation of pragmatic considerations in favour of lived experience (e.g. overall funding envelope, banking system availability and ease of transfer).

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Cash transfers are generally considered to be efficient and cost-effective interventions globally. However, evidence on cost-effectiveness is generally scarce. Doocy and Tappis (2016) focused on identifying costs, efficiency and cost-effectiveness of cash transfer programmes in humanitarian settings. They noted high variability in programmes, with costs per beneficiary ranging from \$11 to \$52. Costs per transfer also varied widely but were noted to be lower for a transfer of cash compared to offer of in-kind goods (\$0.41 on average). Studies demonstrated cost-effectiveness of programmes, particularly unconditional cash transfers, however these were highly context specific. Across its own humanitarian programmes, the International Rescue Committee estimates efficiency of unconditional cash transfer programmes at \$0.14 per dollar transferred up to \$0.61 per dollar transferred in routine scaled programmes (IRC 2015).

However, programme resource requirements are relatively high, and implementation often difficult. Many low-income countries struggle to put in place scalable programmes due to poor banking and administrative infrastructure. Budgets for cash transfer programmes in such settings are also highly donor-dependent, bringing into question the sustainability of programmes for national governments. These conclusions also apply in humanitarian settings (Mikulak 2018), although it is important to recognise that cash transfers may

not be an appropriate intervention for some emergency contexts (see next section). Jeong and Trako (2022) similarly note that while monetary transfers are more efficient to deliver than other modalities (e.g. manual cash, vouchers, in-kind etc,) there has been a severe lack of cost-effectiveness evaluations in humanitarian settings.

Of particular relevance for this review, the evidence base generally does not directly consider mental health outcomes and most studies focus on ascertaining effects while programmes are ongoing or immediately post-cessation. The work of Haushofer et al. (2020) noted above provides one of the few recent examples of consideration of both mental health outcomes and cost-effectiveness. The nominal cost of offering PM+ amounted to \$1189/ recipient, whereas the cash transfer programme only incurred \$485/recipient. The authors conclude that cash transfers prove more cost-effective than the other interventions considered (PM+ and PM+ in combination with cash transfers), but that this result may only hold in so far as the populations live in economic deprivation.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Cash transfer programmes are generally designed to allow scaling, however, the challenge for these programmes relates to securing sustained adoption and ensuring that adoption captures all relevant groups. For example, programmes that use official documentation and/or country residence as a prerequisite for payment often prove inaccessible to informal migrants and/or refugees. Where persons need to prove eligibility for cash transfer programmes, and where clear information on eligibility criteria is lacking, frequent administrative errors occur. This compromises access and acceptability of programmes for both implementers and potential beneficiaries.

Interviewees point to other implementation challenges, including: “lack of trained and qualified staff at the service end (who can perpetuate stigma, pressure potential beneficiaries on the use of cash, provide inadequate information about the programme, and even cases of corruption), bureaucracy (which can also hinder access), and lack of monitoring and accountability of the programme.”

There are particular challenges in ensuring cash transfers are scaled and adopted by national governments in LMICs. Interviewed stakeholders noted that due to limited government capacity and fiscal space, programmes in these settings are often implemented by third parties and funded by major donors. Expansion of programmes is critically dependent on political will and windows of opportunity for action. For example, some funders noted that expansion was easier during COVID-19 given substantive political support in the context of the pandemic. Further, funders noted that mental health impacts are not usually sufficiently featured in policy conversations around adoption. Importantly, health economic evidence on costs of care averted on mental or physical health complications and long-term treatment due to intervention via cash transfers has been flagged as a potential lever for influencing policymakers.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

Cash transfers are a major poverty alleviation mechanism that, as noted above, has been scaled considerably following COVID-19. Universal basic income can be considered a more advanced version of the intervention with huge potential for poverty alleviation and addressing unmet social needs. Machado et al. (2024) review cash transfer programmes (including welfare programmes using this mechanism) across different countries and note that associated reductions in income disparity further reduce national income inequalities (examples include Brazil, Chile and Mexico).

Principal challenges in ensuring that programmes can achieve such outcomes relate to their design and implementation. Some programmes may enhance stigmatisation (see PLE considerations) and may also disrupt social cohesion. In turn, if programmes do not carefully calibrate payments made with a view to redressing existing income inequality, it can be that inequities are exacerbated.

It is also important to consider how cash transfers and situations of emergency interact. For example, Cho & Molina (2023) used panel data from the Philippines in the context of COVID-19 to study this. The Philippines had already rolled out a conditional cash transfer programme (4P), however given the extreme financial shock of COVID-19 on households, the government further made an unconditional emergency payment to vulnerable households. The study authors compared depression rates for those under the qualifying threshold for 4P with those just above the threshold. They found that “rates of severe depression were similar for both groups prior to the pandemic (around 1%), but significantly lower for 4Ps beneficiaries as of July 2020. While depression increased for both groups, it increased substantially more for non-4Ps households (33 percentage points) than 4Ps households (23 percentage points). This is in spite of the more generous emergency cash transfers that were distributed to both groups.” Following substantive sensitivity analyses, Cho and Molina (2024) conclude that the cash transfer programme 4P had large protective effects that were only evident in crisis.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and lessons learned:

Cash transfers generally are at the Adopt stage of the pipeline; there is evidence of programme implementation across all global regions and countries of diverse income levels. Investments by funders in documenting effectiveness of programmes, as well as generally making implementation guides available, helped demonstrate benefits of the intervention at the **Improve & Test** stage and significantly influenced likelihood of adoption. **Scaling and adoption** were facilitated by high levels of political and funder support both in terms of facilitating funding and implementation. This lesson can apply more widely to other interventions where funders could strategically invest in evaluations to drive early progress in the development of interventions of significant potential and wide application. Circumstances that can catalyse political will (for example like COVID-19 or events which call for high social investment) have also acted as facilitators.

Barriers which impact on improvement, scaling and adoption of cash transfer programmes for mental health specifically are varied. First, there is limited knowledge of which types of programme are most effective and present value for money for scaling (and under what circumstances). Second, supportive tools (e.g. digital administration and monitoring and evaluation tools) that can assist scaling of the intervention to new settings are also lacking. Third, limited political will for advancing these programmes across all countries, and lack of funding at national levels are also barriers to wide-spread adoption. Lack of an investment case outlining broad programme benefits was further flagged as inhibiting progress towards widespread adoption a lesson for other interventions. For some countries, where cash transfer programmes are already well embedded – e.g. like the UK where a variety of programmes exist – it is most relevant to consider other potential programme modalities (e.g. universal basic income).

In addition to the above, prominent barriers that impact on development and adoption of the intervention specifically include:

- **Limited evidence in specific populations affected by depression, anxiety, and psychosis.** Global studies on cash transfer programmes are often underpowered for these specific populations and as such we cannot be certain of how effective these programmes are for these sub-groups. For psychosis specifically, the issue of low-prevalence conditions was raised by interviewees; they noted that research in these populations would require larger and longer-term investments in low resource settings given limited diagnostic capacity.
- Gaps in research around which specific programme features are most acceptable, effective, and present best value-for-money for influencing mental health outcomes. Large-scale studies comparing the effectiveness of different cash transfer programme designs (e.g., conditional vs. unconditional transfers, lump-sum vs. regular payments) are essential. These studies should focus not only on economic but also mental health outcomes and consider the lived experience of people with mental health conditions. Where focused on influencing mental health outcomes, studies

should also evaluate cash transfer programme performance against alternative relevant interventions (e.g., psychological, or psychosocial) and consider cost-effectiveness.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- **To enable programme improvement and testing, targeted research in populations with depression, anxiety, and psychosis.** In addition to incentivising targeted research, efforts should be made to collate existing individual-level data through initiatives such as living systematic reviews that incorporate individual patient data wherever possible.
- **To facilitate scaling, comparative effectiveness and cost-effectiveness research.** Investment in large scale studies able to capture effects during and immediately post-programme cessation, as well as long term (i.e. over a 5-10 year time horizon), is needed. Research should also focus on implementation fidelity, cost implications and long-term sustainability, and how varying programme designs influence scalability, equity, and social cohesion in diverse socio-political contexts. Incorporating beneficiaries' perspectives through qualitative research is crucial for understanding how design features impact the acceptability, utilization, and effectiveness of these programmes.
- **Adoption-oriented research and elaboration of investment cases.** To enable wider adoption, research should explore the ecosystems required for effective implementation, scaling, and sustainability of cash transfer programmes. This includes investigating how these programmes alleviate pressures on health and social systems while also addressing broader outcomes such as equity and economic inclusion. Global studies focused on the implementation, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness of different cash transfer models—explicitly considering the burden of mental and physical health alleviated—can strengthen the case for investment. Moreover, research should evaluate the crisis-resilience of cash transfer programmes, ensuring they can be rapidly adapted and scaled in response to diverse shocks, including climate-related disasters and conflicts.

Ecosystem Recommendations

Drawing on consultations and interviews, as well as conclusions from the evidence review, a set of **broader recommendations for investment** can also be identified:

- **Interdisciplinary dialogue for guiding future research.** Interviewees emphasised the need for enhanced dialogue among mental health experts, behavioural economists, policy makers, and cash transfer (CT) implementers to establish common guiding principles for future research. Three key areas were highlighted:
 - a. *Ethical and Pragmatic Challenges in RCTs on Cash Transfers:* Conducting randomised controlled trials (RCTs) on cash transfer programs, particularly in low-resource settings, presents significant ethical and practical challenges. A major concern is the ethical dilemma of randomisation, specifically, the inclusion of control groups that may not receive financial support, despite living in extreme poverty. Establishing ethically sound and methodologically rigorous approaches is essential for research in this area and there is potential for consideration of non-RCT methodologies.

- b. *Ensuring Programme Sustainability and Government Integration*: To promote long-term sustainability, research should focus on stakeholder involvement, particularly in facilitating smooth handovers to national governments. Strong partnerships with governments and implementing agencies were identified as critical for the continuity and effectiveness of cash transfer initiatives. Interviewees recommended that sustainability considerations be built in research.
- c. *Establishing Research Standards*: The field would benefit from clearer research guidelines, which could be elaborated, including on study design considerations (e.g. ensuring trials have sufficient statistical power), research duration (e.g. investing in long-term studies for more comprehensive insights), variable documentation (e.g. systematically recording programme design features and potential confounding factors) and calibration of cash transfer magnitude and duration.

By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and addressing these critical areas, researchers can develop more ethical, sustainable, and methodologically sound approaches to studying cash transfer programs.

- **Expert dialogue and development of (open source) technology and infrastructure.** Cash transfer programmes utilise diverse administrative and digital systems for use. There is a need to convene expert dialogue around key requirements of such systems with a view to potentially support creation of an open-source tool able to enhance programme delivery, reduce administrative inefficiencies, and increase accessibility for vulnerable groups, including migrants and refugees.
- **Enhanced monitoring and evaluation systems.** Similar to the above it would be important to convene policymakers, practitioners, PLE and academics to develop robust, gender-disaggregated and longitudinal monitoring systems to track the outcomes of cash transfers on mental health and poverty alleviation. Continuous evaluation can ensure accountability and refine programme delivery over time.

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CLUBHOUSE MODEL

Pipeline stage: Scale (Partial)

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Director, Program on Clubhouse Research, USA
- Clubhouse Executive, USA
- Professor of Global Mental Health and senior researcher in field of Severe Mental Illness, UK

Target disorders:

Designed to support individuals diagnosed with severe mental health conditions - schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, and bipolar disorder - while also extending its benefits to those experiencing major depressive and anxiety disorders.

Overview of intervention:

The Clubhouse intervention is a community-based, psychosocial rehabilitation approach that emphasises member empowerment, peer support, and work-ordered days (providing a structured daily routine where individuals participate in running the clubhouse based on their interests) to foster recovery and community integration for individuals with mental illness. Developed through pioneering efforts such as those at Fountain House, the model focuses on creating a non-clinical environment where members contribute to decision-making and participate in meaningful activities that promote self-esteem and reduce hospitalisation rates. This holistic framework has been shown to enhance vocational skills and social functioning and support long-term recovery outcomes (Bond et al 2001; Raeburn et al., 2013).

The Clubhouse Model is implemented in 33 countries worldwide, with 371 accredited Clubhouses supporting individuals with mental health conditions through community-based recovery programmes. Clubhouse International's directory list examples of clubhouses in North America (e.g. United States, Canada, Mexico), Europe (e.g. United Kingdom, Netherlands, Sweden), Asia: (e.g. Japan, South Korea, People's Republic of China, India), Africa (e.g. South Africa, Ghana, Uganda), Oceania (e.g. Australia, New Zealand, Papua New Guinea) and South America (Argentina). This global distribution reflects the adaptability of the Clubhouse Model across diverse cultural and economic contexts. While it is more established in high-income countries, there is a growing presence in low-resource settings, demonstrating its potential to address mental health needs worldwide.

Scope:

This review focuses on documenting the lessons learned through several decades of development of the Clubhouse Model and their implications for further scaling of the approach. The geographical spread of Clubhouse indicates progress to the pipeline stage of Scale but, with the number of Clubhouses modest in terms of the global need, this is recognised as partial. In formulating recommendations, the review thus seeks to document issues that have served as barriers to the uptake of the Clubhouse Model (as well as the factors that have facilitated its adoption) and define evidence gaps that, if addressed, stand to promote wider scaling of the approach.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Key elements of the Clubhouse Model comprise:

- Vocational Rehabilitation: Assisting members in developing skills and obtaining support for return to employment or meaningful work.
- Social Integration: Fostering a community environment that encourages peer support, social

interaction, and the rebuilding of social networks.

- Empowerment and Recovery: Enabling members to participate in decision-making processes and build their self-confidence as part of their recovery journey.
- Holistic Support: Addressing diverse needs such as education, housing, and access to clinical services, when necessary, through community connections.
- Continuity and Transition: Serving as a bridge between clinical treatments and community life, helping members maintain stability over the long term.
- On-site provision of psychiatric services is generally not a feature of the model.

The Clubhouse Model originated in the 1940s when former psychiatric patients from Rockland Psychiatric Centre formed WANA (We Are Not Alone), eventually establishing Fountain House in New York City in 1948. John Beard's arrival in 1955 essentially transformed the organisation from a social club into a psychiatric rehabilitation programme. He emphasised meaningful work and dismantled hierarchies between staff and members, which was a major departure from traditional treatment approaches. Later, NIMH funding helped spread the model nationally in the USA. Rudyard Propst further integrated members into governance and supported the establishment of the International Standards for Clubhouse Programs. Both Beard and Propst challenged the medical model's focus on patients rather than people (Anderson, 1998; Doyle et al 2013).

There are 37 International Standards which are a set of guidelines designed to ensure consistency and quality in the implementation of Clubhouses aimed at providing support for people with mental illness. The 37 standards aim to offer a structured approach to how Clubhouses should operate, including aspects like program activities, staff roles, and member involvement. Yet, questions remain about whether they adequately address the diverse needs of individuals with mental illness or merely present an idealised alternative to conventional treatment (McKay et al., 2018). The concern is that the standards may be too rigid or generic, potentially overlooking the complexity and diversity of people's lived experiences with mental illness. Essentially, the debate is whether these standards represent a one-size-fits-all model that may not fully account for the wide range of needs and challenges that different individuals or communities may face.

However, the International Standards do help specify a clear theory of change by outlining explicit expectations for how the Clubhouse Model should operate. The standards articulate specific elements, such as member participation, work-based rehabilitation, and community integration, that are believed to drive positive outcomes (McKay et al., 2018; McKay, 2024). By providing a structured framework, they offer a blueprint for implementing the model consistently, ensuring that the core principles (like equality and recovery orientation) are maintained through mechanisms that help members experience increased social engagement, improved self-esteem, and greater independence. In the long term, the Clubhouse Model aims to achieve stable employment, secure housing, and sustained mental health recovery, ultimately reducing hospitalisations and enhancing overall quality of life. Rooted in a strengths-based, recovery-oriented framework, the Clubhouse Model seeks to shift the focus from illness to capability, ensuring individuals can lead fulfilling and productive lives within their communities (Agner et al, 2023).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

The Clubhouse Model has demonstrated considerable value in supporting individuals with severe mental illness over its sixty-five-year history. McKay et al.'s (2018) systematic review of 52 studies highlights its effectiveness in improving employment outcomes, reducing hospitalisations, and enhancing quality of life. However, they conclude that, while evidence suggests the Clubhouse represents promising practice, studies using more rigorous methods are required to more clearly document the strength of outcomes. Subsequently, Yan et al. (2021) presented a systematic review and meta-analysis collating findings from seven RCTs conducted regarding Clubhouse programmes in China. This successfully documented large

impacts of engaging with Clubhouse programmes on remission of psychiatric symptomology (SMD > 1.00), promotion of social functioning (SMD > 2.00) and reduction in symptoms of depression and anxiety (SMD > 2.00). The CPQ is an annual survey of Clubhouses that gathers programme level information about Clubhouse characteristics, governance and administration, membership, staffing, unit structure, employment, housing activities, & clubhouse training. This has been a valuable source of information for several studies (including cost-effectiveness analyses considered in a later section). However, with no member level information captured by the CPQ it is not a potential source of data relevant to efficacy and effectiveness. Interviews indicated that researchers engaged in documenting the role of Clubhouse are aware of the need to address gaps in evidence regarding the impact of engagement on members, especially extending the heavily US-oriented evidence-base to other high-income and middle- and low-income settings.

Relevance to PLE:

Clubhouse members describe their experience as one characterised by belonging, flexibility, and empowerment. They report that the environment allows them to navigate their recovery at their own pace, engaging in employment, education, or other social activities as needed (Fjeldsoe et al., 2024). Many emphasise that the Clubhouse is the first setting where they feel truly valued and seen beyond their struggles, contributing to a reestablished sense of agency and normalcy (Fekete et al., 2020).

An interviewee with wide experience of work with people with lived experience of severe mental health conditions suggested that the emphasis of Clubhouse was on aspects of recovery crucially valued by PLE. This included support for employment and economic activity but, more generally, *'the satisfaction of being engaged in something productive with others'*.

The overall model aims to provide a structured environment that offers purpose and equality by positioning members as active contributors rather than passive recipients of care. A recent study of lived experience at Fountain House featuring the direct contribution of persons with severe mental illness in all stages of the research process confirmed 'the centrality of action, agency, and meaningful activity in the lives and recovery journeys' of members (Vescey et al. 2023). One member is reported as noting *'I feel like I've made some very strong relationships with members as well as staff working on... projects and it makes me feel like I can accomplish things...this is a place that I always want to volunteer and be able to come to, whether it's a Thursday night or a work-ordered day, I see it as a part of my life...for a long time.'* The study also illustrated, however, where members considered the work of the Clubhouse could be strengthened, particularly in relation to addressing evolving needs of members in later stages of their recovery.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Although there isn't a large body of rigorous cost-effectiveness research exclusively on the Clubhouse Model, available evidence indicates a favourable cost-benefit outcome, particularly when reduced hospitalisation costs and improved social participation are considered.

Two studies emphasise the potential cost-effectiveness of the Clubhouse Model in the US in supporting individuals with severe mental health conditions while reducing overall healthcare costs. Gorman (2012) demonstrated that for every dollar spent on employment services members earned \$1.31, and for every hour a staff member dedicates to employment services members earned \$38.73. This suggests that the resources invested in employment support not only helps individuals achieve financial independence but also contribute to reduced reliance on more intensive mental health services. The median investment of 121 hours and \$3,438 per member employed for at least six months further supports the view that Clubhouse programmes can deliver a high return on investment in terms of member earnings and reduced public service costs. Usman and Seidman (2024) found that the Clubhouse Model could save more than \$11,000 per person annually when considering the full spectrum of social and public costs. With an

estimated 60,000 individuals attending clubhouses in the USA at that time, this translated to nearly \$700 million in national savings each year. The authors noted that the savings would be significantly higher if a greater proportion of the estimated 15 million people in the USA with severe mental health conditions had access to these programmes.

In terms of broader cost analysis of the Clubhouse Model, McKay et al. 2007 noted significant variability in the financial structure of the model across twelve countries. Total annual programme budgets ranged from \$40,145 to \$1,461,100, with a mean of \$408,082 and a median of \$350,000 in 2000. The mean cost per member per year was \$3,203, with a broad range from \$247 to \$8,571, and the mean cost per visit was \$27.12, varying between \$2.33 and \$80.01. The analysis found that the total budget of a clubhouse correlated significantly with both the cost per member ($r = .46$) and the cost per visit ($r = .41$), indicating that larger budgets tend to lead to higher costs in both areas. Additionally, cost per member and cost per visit were positively correlated ($r = .52$), suggesting that higher membership costs generally correspond to higher per-visit costs. These findings highlight the variability in operational costs depending on factors such as size, scope of services, and funding, underscoring the importance of sustainable funding sources and efficient resource allocation to ensure the scalability and sustainability of the model.

While the overall picture is positive, with indications that Clubhouse programmes can be cost effective due to reduced reliance on inpatient services and the promotion of employment—the research base is still very restricted, and very focused on the USA. Further large-scale studies are needed for a more definitive conclusion on cost effectiveness in a broader range of settings.

Context, applicability and scalability:

There are currently 371 accredited Clubhouses globally, across 33 countries (McKay, 2024). Advocacy and capacity development through Clubhouse International appears to have been the major driver in this increase from around just 35 Clubhouses being in existence in the 1990s. Clubhouses are more common in high- and middle-income settings (across North America, Europe, East Asia, Australasia and Latin America) although there are now examples in settings such as sub-Saharan Africa (e.g. South Africa, Ghana) and the western Pacific (i.e. Papua New Guinea). Although there is little information on the operation of Clubhouses in LMICs, an interviewee with wide experience in such settings considered that they may play a valuable role *'providing a key resource between primary-care-based community provision and tertiary institutions given the general lack of secondary care in such settings'*.

Adapting Clubhouse for implementation across diverse cultural and socio-economic contexts – but in a manner that retains the key principles reflected in the Clubhouse Standards – is both crucial and demanding (Matsui et al., 2013). One interviewee observed that there was a risk that the peer-led element of the Clubhouse Model could be diluted, with staff assuming roles and modelling a culture more associated with standard daycare provision.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

While the Clubhouse Model promotes inclusion, true equity requires expanding access in underserved regions, reducing barriers for the most marginalised groups, and ensuring cultural adaptability. The Clubhouse Model is designed to be inclusive, primarily serving individuals with severe mental health conditions who often face social and economic marginalisation. However, equity challenges exist in terms of who accesses these services. In high-income countries, Clubhouses may serve both marginalised and more privileged groups, but access can still be influenced by location, awareness, and systemic barriers (e.g. individuals with severe disabilities or those experiencing homelessness may struggle to engage; Matsui et al., 2013). One interviewee also noted that settings such as a Clubhouse – with their strong social dynamic - need to make very intentional actions to ensure equity of access – and sense of safety and inclusion – with regards to gender, age and sexuality.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Clubhouse has provided a model of support for individuals with severe mental health conditions emphasising the fostering of community connection and peer empowerment. Many members value this approach for providing a space where they feel truly recognised and supported offering a welcomed contrast to traditional mental health care.

However, several challenges remain. Integrating a peer-led model with conventional clinical services is reported to be complex, particularly in the absence of on-site psychiatric support. At the heart of the Clubhouse approach is a recovery-oriented, non-clinical ethos that emphasises mutuality, empowerment, and community participation, often led and co-designed by people with lived experience of mental illness. This can stand in contrast to traditional clinical models, which are typically hierarchical, diagnosis-driven, and centred on professional expertise and risk management. Mental health systems are organised around medicalised care pathways, making it difficult to recognise or value peer-led contributions as legitimate forms of support. This mismatch can lead to tensions in coordination, role ambiguity, or even resistance from clinicians unaccustomed to shared decision-making models. These challenges become even more pronounced in settings where on-site psychiatric support is absent, potentially limiting the Clubhouse's ability to refer members for timely medical or psychiatric care when needed.

Cultural adaptation poses an additional hurdle. Originating in the United States, the model does not always resonate seamlessly in diverse cultural contexts and thus demands thoughtful adjustments to align with local values and understandings of mental health.

Moreover, while the model's low overhead and emphasis on community resources suggest potential for use in low-income settings, evidence of successful widespread adoption in such environments is limited. The challenge lies in meeting essential requirements—such as secure space and trained staff—under conditions where even basic health services may be scarce. In settings with robust healthcare infrastructure, its integration with clinical services can be more straightforward. In contrast, low-resource environments might benefit from the lower overhead costs and community-driven principles, though these same settings often face the additional challenge of limited resources to support the necessary infrastructure.

In summary, while the Clubhouse Model offers transformative benefits through its community-driven approach, its long-term success will depend on overcoming funding uncertainties, effectively adapting to cultural and resource constraints, and ensuring that support structures promote gradual independence. As one interviewee noted: *'The economic and cultural challenges in some places are substantial... those are the places where most people living with mental illness are not getting help at all.'*

While the Clubhouse Model has shown promise in supporting individuals with mental health challenges, there are several critical research gaps that need to be addressed to strengthen the model, improve its outcomes, and support its expansion.

- 1. Long term impact studies:** One of the most significant gaps is the lack of long-term impact studies. While the Clubhouse Model has been shown to provide immediate benefits, such as improved social integration and engagement, there is limited research that tracks the long-term effects on members in terms of recovery. It is essential to understand how sustained participation in Clubhouses influences overall life outcomes over several years. Long-term studies would provide valuable insights into whether the model leads to lasting improvements not only in mental health, but also in employment, housing stability, and community participation.
- 2. Cost-effectiveness analyses:** Another research gap is the need for further cost-effectiveness analyses. Although the Clubhouse Model is often suggested as being relatively low-cost compared to other mental health interventions, demonstrating its economic benefits across a broader range

of settings (the current evidence-base is heavily biased towards US data) would significantly strengthen its case for wider scaling through public funding. In particular, research that quantifies the costs and long-term savings associated with reduced healthcare utilization (e.g. fewer hospitalizations or crisis interventions) may assist in securing more financial support from government bodies and other funding sources.

- 3. Population specificity and unintended consequences:** There is uncertainty about how effectively the model addresses the needs of various, potentially underrepresented, populations. Some critics have noted that because the Clubhouse Model does not incorporate onsite psychiatry clinics this may limit its effectiveness for individuals with more acute needs. Additionally, there are suggestions that the model may promote long-term service dependence rather than fostering complete independence (Raeburn et al., 2013). Questions have also arisen about whether it may inadvertently reinforce isolation for some groups or restrict full integration into broader communities.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- **Promoting research activity to address the three research gaps** indicated above would provide a significantly stronger evidence-base on which to base decisions regarding the wider promotion of the Clubhouse Model as a scalable model of intervention for persons with severe mental illness globally. Clearly, investing in research to demonstrate the effectiveness and long-term impact of the Clubhouse Model is essential for gaining broader recognition within healthcare systems. This research should focus on both the benefits of the model and the cost-effectiveness. Further, it is critical that this research reflects a broad range of contexts (high-, middle- and low-income) if it is to form an evidence-base that can support scaling across these different settings.

Ecosystem Recommendations

In addition, however, further scaling of the Clubhouse Model would require attention to other investments regarding such issues as sustainability, quality control, innovation in delivery, cultural adaptation and advocacy:

- **Identify sustainable funding sources.** To ensure the continued growth and sustainability of the Clubhouse Model, there needs to be a diversified mix of funding sources. While government funding plays a significant role, securing additional public and private investments would be crucial to any significant move to wider adoption. By advocating for more widespread investment - from governmental healthcare systems, philanthropies and the private sector (the latter relevant in terms of the agendas of both employment and corporate social responsibility) - the model can become less vulnerable to the fragility of any one funding stream. This would also enable Clubhouses to scale more effectively and reach more people in need. As one Clubhouse advocate interviewed noted: *'We need public and private funding to support drive this vision for global scaling ... how do we really get this model out there?'*
- **Develop scalable training models.** Investment in the development of scalable and accessible training models is essential. With the growing need for Clubhouses worldwide, creating training programs that are digital, remote, or accessible through other innovative methods would allow for more efficient replication of the model. Ensuring that new and existing Clubhouses can maintain

high-quality standards without requiring excessive time or resources for training staff is critical. By investing in scalable training solutions, the Clubhouse Model can expand rapidly while maintaining its integrity and effectiveness. One stakeholder interviewed, when asked about what was required to support scaling, responded: *'Access to training and support in a way that's different than what we have now...[but] we need to continue to manage quality and fidelity'*.

- **Encourage innovation in delivery.** The COVID-19 pandemic provided some valuable learning for the Clubhouse movement (Michon et al., 2021). The Clubhouse Model could usefully leverage the potential of digital platforms and emerging technologies. Investment in the integration of digital tools—such as AI, virtual platforms for remote support, and digital monitoring systems—could improve the efficiency and accessibility of the model. By incorporating innovation into the delivery of services, Clubhouses can extend their reach, particularly to regions that lack the physical infrastructure for traditional services. Investing in technological solutions could help modernise the model and create a more scalable and adaptable version of the Clubhouse for future generations.
- **Support cultural and contextual adaptation.** Allocate resources for adapting the model to different cultural contexts, ensuring that program design aligns with local values, practices, and needs. In addition to investing in capacity-building, training, and implementation support to help local organisations tailor the model effectively in low-income or diverse cultural settings.
- **Stronger advocacy efforts** are needed to raise awareness among policymakers, mental health professionals, and the public. Increased investment in these areas will help garner the support needed for wider adoption and funding

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LET'S WALK TOGETHER PROGRAMME (EMPLOYMENT-BASED)

Pipeline stage: Prototype exemplar

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Co-founder of Let's Walk Together (LWT) and serves as Co-Founder & Managing Trustee of the PLE-led organisation that implements LWT. Is also a member of the core team that supports LWT. Lived experience of bipolar disorder and public advocate, India.
- Programme Lead of LWT, oversees day-to-day implementation since its inception. Lived experience of bipolar disorder, India.
- Donor, initially involved as advisor to LWT in conceptualising intervention, and later funder of LWT development and implementation (stepping back from advisory role), India.

Target disorders:

The initiative targets severe mental health conditions that present significant challenges for maintaining consistent employment, especially bipolar disorder and schizophrenia.

Overview of intervention:

Let's Walk Together (LWT) is a supported employment intervention initiated in 2021 in Mumbai, India. LWT's development was in response to a perceived gap in support for persons living with severe mental health conditions to continue or access work within corporate sector employment. LWT comprises multiple components, including a) supporting adoption of inclusive corporate workplace policies for people with severe mental health conditions, b) training of human resource managers and senior managers to sensitise workplaces to the needs of PLE employees, c) facilitating job opportunities for PLE, and d) mentoring candidates with mental health conditions to apply for work opportunities and manage workplace challenges. LWT also provides a platform to match candidates with diagnoses of severe mental health conditions to vacant positions in corporate organisations. LWT differs from the similar Individual Placement and Support intervention in that it carries out activities with corporate employers in addition to placing and supporting candidates in work. In addition, the leadership and staff of LWT is exclusively PLE, as is the core team of corporate peer mentors, whilst there are mental health professionals represented on the advisory group that supported its development.

Scope:

Due to the lack of published evaluation data on the Let's Walk Together (LWT) Programme, this deep dive has been compiled using available relevant information obtained through interviews with core team members, an internal programme document provided by LWT, and an interview with one of the programme's funders. Given the limited data available on LWT, discussion of the approach is also supplemented with evidence on a similar intervention, Individual Placement and Support.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Let's Walk Together (LWT) is an initiative conceptualised by a PLE advocate and founder of PLE-led organisations to address the challenges faced by individuals with severe mental health conditions in accessing and sustaining employment in corporate employment. Launched in August 2021 as a self-funded initiative of a volunteer-run PLE-led organisation, LWT focuses on enhancing the economic participation of individuals with mental health conditions in urban settings, responding specifically to the

lack of interventions for urban white-collar workplace placement and support for individuals with severe mental health conditions such as bipolar disorder or schizophrenia.

The programme was developed in the context of national legislation (India's Mental Health Act 2017 and the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016) that advanced the rights of persons with mental health conditions, including their right to non-discrimination and reasonable accommodation within the workplace. While many corporate Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) initiatives existed, mental health was considered an overlooked and stigmatised aspect of workplace inclusivity.

LWT's intervention logic recognises that economic participation and employment can be a key factor in preventing relapse as well as supporting the recovery of persons with mental health conditions, and also that workplace stress or loss of employment can precipitate significant decline in mental health for PLE. As such, LWT's model comprises three main components that seek to strengthen access to supportive employment: a) promoting workplace sensitisation and readiness; b) matching PLE candidates with suitable vacancies; and c) support to PLE candidates and employees.

LWT identifies that stigma, lack of workplace sensitisation and the risks of disclosure prevent individuals with mental health conditions from accessing necessary accommodations. Through engaging with corporates through testimonies and advocacy by PLE, especially prominent corporate leaders with mental health conditions, LWT seeks to assist companies in developing legally mandated Equal Opportunity Policy documents (required under Indian disability law) that outline the accommodations that companies will make for persons with mental health conditions. In addition, training is offered to human resources staff, managers and corporate leadership to sensitise them to considerations in recruiting, managing and working alongside PLE.

LWT identifies potential placements through direct engagement with corporates, as well as through collaborations with disability inclusion organisations with similar placement activities. LWT then supports PLE in seeking employment through 'matching' via its job portal.

LWT provides support at each stage of the employment process – from job-seeking to recruitment and managing work. It seeks to do this by providing one-on-one mentoring via regular (sometimes weekly) check-ins by senior corporate leaders with lived experience, occasional training on job-seeking (ie. CV writing, job selection or interview preparation) and employment-related issues (ie. navigating disclosure or dealing with work stress), and facilitation of peer support and exchange via a group on a messaging app. As part of iterative developments within the ongoing pilot initiative, a train-the-trainers module for peer mentors was in the process of being developed (at the time of LWT interviews) on the basis of practical experience of LWT implementation to date.

Whilst the programme's activities are distinct and independent, LWT is indirectly strengthened by its loose affiliation and proximity with a larger peer network facilitated by a PLE-led organisation – which is an additional source of social and practical support for participants in LWT.

The potential impacts of LWT were perceived by interviewees to be at two levels. The primary impact was via LWT's direct enabling of sustained employment of PLE with severe mental health conditions, maintaining and enhancing their recovery. In addition, it was also felt, especially by the donor interviewee, that increased scale and visibility of LWT could be a catalyst for broader change, shifting perceptions and norms within the corporate sector and wider society about supportive and accommodative employment that could improve employment opportunities for PLE in general, even beyond the direct reach of programmes like LWT.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Since LWT is a relatively new intervention still in its early stages of implementation, no studies have yet assessed its efficacy or effectiveness through formal evaluation. This represents a significant gap in the

evidence base. However, a comparable intervention, Individual Placement and Support (IPS), has been extensively studied and shown to be effective in helping individuals secure and maintain competitive employment (See the IPS deep dive included in this annex).

Given the strong evidence supporting IPS's effectiveness, it is reasonable to hypothesise that LWT may yield similar outcomes, as both interventions are grounded in shared principles, such as person-centred support, a focus on individual goals, and an emphasis on supported employment for people with mental health conditions. Both programmes respond to a recognition that people with mental health conditions face significant challenges in finding and keeping jobs, and are designed to address these challenges through tailored, practical support. LWT differs from IPS in being conceptualised as being PLE-led and implemented, rather than staffed by non-PLE employment specialists, and also in actively engaging with prospective employers to facilitate appropriate accommodations and readiness to recruit and support PLE employees ((Elkin & Freedman, 2020). These deviations from the IPS model may represent valuable innovation, but to confirm this, comparative research is needed. While LWT has not yet undergone evaluation, IPS's well-documented success—demonstrating higher employment rates, faster job attainment, and improved job retention—suggests that LWT may achieve comparable results, especially with the ongoing refinement of the peer mentoring model and inclusion of employer-side intervention components. The consistency of IPS's effectiveness across multiple studies further supports this expectation.

At present, there is no trials or implemented studies directly comparing LWT to IPS or other similar employment support models. To strengthen the evidence base, it is critical to undertake rigorous studies (such as feasibility trials, implementation evaluations, or mixed-methods comparisons) that can assess whether LWT achieves similar or greater outcomes, for whom, and under what conditions. Without this evidence, assumptions about LWT's effectiveness remain speculative, even if grounded in well-established principles. A comparative evaluation would also help determine whether the added components of peer-led delivery and employer engagement contribute meaningfully to outcomes.

Relevance to PLE:

The staff and core team (also peer mentors) of the LWT programme are composed of PLE. This intentional approach seeks to ensure that the programme remains deeply connected to the authentic challenges and needs of those navigating mental health conditions. According to interviewees, this approach ensures that the LWT programme is grounded fundamentally in lived experience and plays a critical role in shaping its strategic direction and operational priorities. The core team members have considerable experience of building careers in corporate employment whilst living with severe mental health conditions, and this has shaped programme design, informed peer support strategies, and been critical to building trust with PLE job candidates through shared, relevant understanding. Their insights help the programme to anticipate and deal with challenges faced by PLE, while also modelling recovery and leadership.

Although direct information on the acceptability of LWT to PLE participants was not possible to obtain, the PLE-led nature of the intervention suggests it is likely acceptable to its intended users, as suggested by interviewees.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

The programme operates through the voluntary contributions of its dedicated core team members, who effectively balance their professional responsibilities with their strong commitment to LWT. At this stage, the team has not undertaken any formal cost-effectiveness evaluation of the programme's operations.

Individual Placement and Support (IPS) (See the IPS deep dive included in this annex) has been widely recognised as a cost-effective approach in studies conducted in the United States and England (Drake et al., 2023; Marsden et al., 2024). The primary expenses within IPS include staffing, supervision, and overhead, averaging approximately \$6,000 per client annually. Compared to standard employment support

services, IPS is often both more effective and more economical. In some cases, cost-effectiveness studies suggest that IPS may lead to overall cost savings when compared to alternative programmes. Recent trials further support IPS's cost-effectiveness in improving quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) for individuals with substance use disorders, using a £70,000 willingness-to-pay (WTP) threshold. Additionally, IPS has been found to be cost-effective in increasing employment among individuals with alcohol use disorder, at a WTP threshold of £200 per additional workday (Drake et al., 2023; Marsden et al., 2024).

When relating these findings to the Let's Walk Together (LWT) programme, it is important to consider potential differences in cost and benefit profiles. Differences in cost across national economies notwithstanding, LWT currently operates with minimal paid staff, and considerable volunteer contributions of peer mentors, which may keep its costs comparatively significantly lower than IPS which relies on fully paid staff. LWT interviewees indicated that the primary costs at present are more on infrastructure (ie. office rent) than personnel. As LWT scales up participation, there may be initial further gains in cost-per-client with this model, but these may be offset by the need to increase supervision and management capacity to manage greater numbers of participants, staff and other activities.

Given other similarities between IPS and LWT, it is reasonable to expect that LWT will demonstrate at least comparable cost-effectiveness. Considering IPS's success in reducing costs while enhancing employment outcomes and quality of life, LWT is likely to achieve similar benefits. This suggests that LWT may serve as a promising option for intervention in this area.

Context, applicability and scalability:

The LWT programme was introduced during the COVID-19 pandemic, a period that significantly heightened awareness of mental health challenges and led to greater corporate flexibility through remote work arrangements. This initiative emerged at a crucial time, aligning with the increasing legal and social recognition of the importance of mental well-being and the need for inclusive workplace practices. The programme is designed to be adaptable to any corporate environments in India, especially those beginning to engage with inclusive workplace practices and showing interest in supporting employees with lived experience of mental health challenges. However, its ability to expand is currently limited by staffing and resource constraints. Despite these challenges, the programme has substantial potential for growth, provided it receives additional funding and institutional support.

A notable strength of the LWT programme is its active and growing engagement with employers and entrepreneurs, particularly in the context of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act (2016) and the Mental Health Act (2017) that protect PLE from discrimination and enhance their employment rights. This engagement creates a dual impact: a 'pull' factor, encouraging the development of employment opportunities for PLE, and a 'push' factor, emphasising the importance of inclusive workplace practices. An interviewee highlighted that India presents a particularly favourable environment for the LWT programme due to its supportive policy landscape. The programme demonstrates significant potential for replication, particularly in regions where chronic youth unemployment exacerbates mental health challenges. However, successful replication requires a clearer understanding of the legal, social, and economic conditions necessary for its sustainability. These conditions are important because the effectiveness of LWT relies not only on the presence of supportive policies but also on their application in diverse regions. For example, the local legal framework may be key to ensuring the protection of the rights of persons with disabilities and motivating employers to create inclusive employment opportunities. Additionally, social conditions, such as cultural perceptions of mental health and disability, will significantly impact the program's adoption and success. In a context where these conducive factors exist, the LWT programme could serve as a scalable and effective model for integrating mental health support with employment inclusivity.

Several barriers hinder the effective implementation and scaling of the programme, many of which are deeply rooted in societal and structural challenges. A major obstacle is the persistent stigma surrounding

mental health, which, coupled with fears of discrimination, often prevents PLE from disclosing their conditions in the workplace. This reluctance is further compounded by a general lack of awareness and the absence of inclusive policies within corporate environments, which fail to create a supportive and accommodating workspace for individuals with mental health challenges. Additionally, practical constraints such as limited resources and staffing restrict the programme's ability to expand its reach and impact.

Conversely, several key facilitators contribute to the programme's growth. Collaboration with disability inclusion organisations has provided essential support, offering both expertise and resources. The COVID-19 pandemic also played an unexpected role in fostering greater societal awareness of mental health issues, creating a more receptive environment for initiatives like the LWT programme. As individuals and organisations become increasingly attuned to the importance of mental well-being in both personal and professional contexts, these facilitators provide a strong foundation for the continued development and success of the programme.

The LWT interviewees emphasised the symbolic and practical significance of implementation by PLE, as which they stated increased trust and confidence in the programme content, especially in the case of peer mentors who were able to relate to the experiences of employment as a persons with similar mental health conditions to the candidates. According to one interviewee, successfully replicating LWT in other settings requires an existing PLE-led organisation or peer network. Implementors of LWT must also have good entry-points and connections with the corporate sector and a deep understanding of business practices and ways of working. Engaging senior-level PLE professionals from various organisations as active members of this implementation team is also essential. Moreover, the implementors must have the capacity to provide policy guidance and strengthen the skills and readiness of both corporate partners and job candidates, ensuring they are prepared to apply for relevant positions. Securing financial resources is crucial for sustaining these efforts, and an interviewee emphasised that funding should be framed as advocacy rather than as a direct intervention. *"You will need a supporting mechanism that this organisation will need to provide in terms of policy support, capacity building of the corporates, as well as capacity building of these profiles or community members so that they can apply for relevant jobs, and this effort will need to be funded because it's advocacy. And it will need to be funded as advocacy rather than an intervention"*.

In comparison to IPS, which has scaled across over 20 mostly high-income countries (Drake & Bond, 2023), both models face adaptation challenges in low-resource settings. IPS requires high-fidelity implementation, which can limit feasibility in informal or high-unemployment economies. However, its core principles may still be adaptable using local structures and community-based supports (See the IPS deep dive included in this annex), similar to LWT.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

LWT is dedicated to addressing the often-hidden nature of mental health disorders and the stigma that frequently prevents PLE from disclosing their conditions in the workplace. The programme advocates for reasonable adjustments and equitable opportunities, ensuring that PLE are treated fairly and protected from discrimination. Through awareness-raising initiatives and the promotion of understanding, LWT strives to cultivate a supportive work environment where individuals feel safe to openly discuss their mental health without fear of judgment or bias, allowing them to thrive professionally.

As one interviewee highlighted, the inclusion of psychosocial disabilities within the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016, as one of the 21 recognised disabilities, serves as a crucial safeguard against discrimination. This legal framework mandates the inclusion of PLE in corporate settings, reinforcing their right to equal participation in the workforce.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Despite its promising approach, questions remain about the potential replicability and long-term sustainability of LWT. Purely PLE-led and implemented interventions are relatively uncommon, raising questions about how similar leadership can be easily found in other settings, or how a consistent leadership pipeline can be maintained beyond the founders. Additionally, whereas IPS has been supported by a formal evidence base and systematised guidance, it is uncertain how well this model can be adapted across different cultural, economic, and corporate environments beyond Mumbai or India, especially in regions with higher levels of stigma surrounding mental health or less developed workplace inclusivity policies, and where PLE leadership may not be as strong.

One major barrier to LWT's success is the persistent stigma associated with mental health conditions. Many PLEs face challenges in openly disclosing their conditions due to fear of discrimination, which can limit their ability to advocate for accommodations, unlike IPS, where professionals often act as intermediaries. Moreover, workplace policies are often insufficiently inclusive, and a lack of awareness among employers further compounds these challenges. Limited staffing and financial constraints also restrict LWT's capacity to expand and sustain its activities at a larger scale, in contrast of IPS, which has benefited from structured funding and formal implementation models in several contexts.

However, several factors facilitate the advancement of this initiative. Collaboration with disability inclusion organisations has proven beneficial in strengthening LWT's credibility and outreach. The programme's leadership by individuals with lived experience ensures that interventions remain relevant and directly aligned with the needs of PLE. Additionally, societal shifts in attitudes toward mental health—partly influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic—have created a more receptive environment for workplace mental health initiatives.

For LWT to advance, it must first demonstrate effectiveness in achieving its core goals. This includes evaluating outcomes such as job retention, participant mental health status and wellbeing, and employer engagement. Building a stronger evidence base around these outcomes will not only validate the programme's current impact but also lay the groundwork for sustainability. To ensure long-term success, LWT will need to address sustainability concerns such as securing stable funding, forging strategic corporate partnerships, and investing in internal capacity-building. Learning from IPS, which has benefited from the development of learning communities and clear implementation tools, LWT could consider how to formalise its model and support future adaptation. Robust research on the programme's effectiveness, especially regarding workplace accommodations for PLE, will be key to influencing broader policy and institutional practices in support of inclusive employment.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations:

- **Evaluating the effectiveness of the LWT programme** is a necessary condition for further investment or development of the model. There is a need to generate empirical evidence that demonstrates the programme's effectiveness in securing sustained employment and recovery for PLE, including for the target conditions. In conjunction with this, it may be useful to examine the scope for modest scaling up and replicability of the model in similar and diverse contexts.
- Invest in research and innovation in comparable placement programmes and broader workforce support systems with significant PLE leadership and involvement in implementation, as LWT has highlighted both a gap in a key area for intervention as well as potentially promising elements for PLE inclusion, which may go beyond the current LWT model.
- Invest in economic evaluation for LWT. While it could be inferred that LWT suggest positive outcomes

in supporting people with mental health conditions seeking employment, there is a lack of a formal economic evaluation. Targeted investment should support both the programme delivery and cost-effectiveness studies to assess the impact of the intervention to help make a stronger case to policymakers and funders for long-term support.

- Generate implementation evidence to support scale-up. To move toward broader replication, investment must focus on evidence related to scaling, such as how the programme adapts across diverse settings, what support systems are needed, and how it can be integrated with existing public health policies and employment schemes.
- Fund comparative research between LWT and similar interventions (IPS). Comparative implementation research can help clarify which model, or if a combination of elements from both, leads to better outcomes depending on the context, guiding more effective and scalable employment support strategies,

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INDIVIDUAL PLACEMENT AND SUPPORT (SUPPORTED EMPLOYMENT)

Pipeline stage: Scale

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Emeritus Professor of Psychiatry, Senior Researcher, focused on IPS for over 25 years including development of model and assessment of fidelity across global settings.
- Lecturer and Occupational Therapist, University of Zimbabwe.

Target disorders:

Supported employment interventions have been primarily used to support persons with psychosis and schizophrenia, and increasingly also bipolar disorder. Applicability to depression and anxiety remains under investigation and the evidence base is sparse.

Overview of intervention:

Supported employment is a category of interventions which seek to assist persons with severe mental illness in gaining access to, securing and maintaining, decent work. There are two intervention models that must be distinguished. Train and place models – which include interventions such as Clubhouse – aim to first equip persons with severe mental illness to gain specific skills needed to secure and maintain employment before placing them in work. In contrast, place and train models – such as the Individual Placement and Support (IPS) model – works to first place persons in work, and then to support them throughout this as long as needed. In both cases, there is an attempt made to place individuals in long-term roles able to offer fair income. Both models include skill-building components and are usually accompanied by care and support offered by an interdisciplinary team. IPS is usually embedded in mental health teams and seeks to connect diagnosed patients with an interdisciplinary support team, including mental health workers and employment specialists, as well as others as relevant (e.g. general practitioners, social workers).

IPS is built on eight fundamental principles:

1. Focus on competitive employment: agencies involved in IPS seek to place individuals in competitive and regular employment at community level.
2. Zero exclusion policy: all clients who want to work are eligible for placement, without the need for additional assessment or screening.
3. Attention to client preferences: rather than rely on professional assessment of where a client should be placed, client preferences guide placement.
4. Rapid job search and placement: clients are rapidly placed after expressing interest, without lengthy pre-vocational assessment.
5. Targeted job development: repeated contact with employers is used to better understand business needs and better target job seeking and placement.
6. Integration of employment and mental health services: multidisciplinary provider teams work together to align mental health and vocational services.
7. Personalised benefits counselling: IPS teams assist clients with obtaining accurate information on eligibility for benefits and other potential entitlements.
8. Individualised long-term support: support is provided for as long as the client needs, across all support domains (mental health, vocational).

Scope:

This deep dive focuses on the most commonly studied model of supported employment – Individual Placement and Support. Where relevant, we will contrast this against other models as noted above.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Individual Placement and Support (IPS) emerged in the 1990s at a community mental health centre in the northeastern United States. It was developed by Deborah Becker and Robert Drake who adapted the supported employment model from the developmental disabilities field. Before IPS, employment approaches for people with severe mental illness relied on extensive pre-vocational training, sheltered workshops, and transitional employment. This assumed that patients were not ready for employment and required significant skill development prior to entering the workplace.

The theory of change underlying IPS represents a shift from this "train-then-place" to "place-then-train" model. IPS posits that by rapidly connecting clients to competitive jobs matching their preferences and providing ongoing support, individuals will experience improved vocational outcomes, clinical stability, and overall well-being. This approach recognises employment as a critical social determinant of health rather than viewing work as something that should only follow clinical recovery. The model emphasises that persons who are supported through IPS regain self-confidence, reduce their dependency on others and are able to fulfil social roles and responsibilities. IPS interventions must also be viewed as distinct from cash transfer interventions and/or welfare programmes; the latter act exclusively on income levels as part of their theory of change, but may not routinely involve employment or related employment supports as part of their intervention pathways.

Over time, IPS has been refined through the development of manuals, fidelity measures, and training programs (Becker et al., 2019). The model has expanded beyond its original focus on severe mental illness to include people with common mental health conditions, substance use disorders, chronic pain, and other disabilities, while maintaining fidelity to core principles. Interviewees flagged several facilitators to the development and implementation of IPS. First, researchers drawing on existing evidence – and listening to persons with lived experience who actively noted that being out of work was a severe barrier to recovery – prompted development of an intervention that is flexible and grounded in lived experience. Champions who could interest practitioners in the intervention and seek funding for implementation and research were also noted as critical. Research which focused on both effectiveness and implementation, rather than efficacy under ideal conditions, helped the research base evolve from small pilots to larger RCTs and establish a solid evidence base that was reflective of practice realities. The research was able to clearly distil principles and key mechanisms of action, which then formed the basis for manuals and fidelity measures that could further accelerate scaling. Learning communities (IPS Grow, n.d.) which help interested practitioners implement the intervention in new settings are also particularly important – they offer access to peers in the implementation process and expert support.

Key barriers to implementation are noted across several studies (Modini et al 2016, Hutchinson et al 2018) and are similar to those noted by interviewees. Barriers include limited integration between mental health, social care, and vocational rehabilitation, often exacerbated by funding constraints. High unemployment and restrictive labour and disability policies create challenging environments for workforce participation. Deep-rooted stigma and misconceptions about the work abilities of people with severe mental illness persist, particularly concerns about job performance and workplace safety. Specific barriers apply when considering scaling and adoption across low-resource settings (see context section).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

The evidence base for IPS is highly evolved. Crowther et al (2001) conducted the first Cochrane review on supported employment interventions in adults of working age with severe mental illness (schizophrenia, bipolar disorder and psychosis or depression with psychotic features). A review of 18 randomised

controlled trials of mixed quality found that supported employment interventions were significantly more effective than pre-vocational training in securing competitive jobs. At 18 months, 34% of supported employment participants were employed versus 12% in pre-vocational training (consisting of sheltered workshop or Clubhouse model – see also Club House deep dive). They also worked more hours and earned higher wages. Pre-vocational training showed no clear advantage over standard community care. However, data on clinical outcomes was extremely sparse, although suggestive of pre-vocational training being associated with likelier hospital discharge.

Kinoshita et al (2013) extended the above analysis and focused specifically on IPS. Across 14 randomised trials (2265 persons), the authors identified similar promising effects of supportive employment on vocational outcomes (RR 3.24 CI 2.17 to 4.82) however the quality of evidence was noted to be very low due to high risk of bias across RCTs, publication bias and inconsistency and imprecision. However, the picture is mixed regarding clinical outcomes. Supported employment shows no significant effects on clinical or service use outcomes compared to other vocational approaches. Symptom severity, quality of life, and general functioning scores (BPRS, PANSS, HADS, QOL-QOLI, GAS) remain similar. Hospital admission rates show mixed findings, with one analysis suggesting a slight reduction (RR 0.71, 95% CI 0.53–0.96) but overall, no clear advantage. There is also no evidence of differences in mortality, adverse effects, or economic costs.

Evidence is supportive of effects being similar across young adults (under 30). Bond, Drake and Campbell (2016) pool results across four randomised trials and note that 82% of IPS participants obtained employment during their follow-up compared to 42% in the control group. Bond et al (2023) extend across an updated review and identify 7 randomised trials (4 on psychosis and 3 on young adult sub-groups with psychotic symptoms). The authors identify IPS benefits (58.3% employment) against controls (32.4, overall RR 1.69 (95% CI 1.43, 1.99). Additionally, six of the seven studies found that the IPS group had longer job durations compared to the control group, with an overall effect size of $g = 0.34$ (95% CI 0.09, 0.58), $z = 2.72$, $p < 0.01$.

Contextual variation in effectiveness for supported employment generally and IPS is to be expected. Modini et al (2016) review evidence on supported employment for persons with severe mental illness globally. They identify 17 studies, focused on USA, Canada, UK, Switzerland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden, Bulgaria, Japan, Australia and Italy. Across these, the authors note that the pooled risk ratio for competitive employment with IPS versus traditional vocational rehabilitation was 2.40 (95% CI 1.99–2.90), indicating significantly greater effectiveness. Meta-regression analysis found that IPS outcomes were not influenced by geographic location or unemployment rates. Even in countries with GDP growth below 2%, IPS remained more effective than traditional vocational training, with benefits persisting beyond two years. However, this review did not include any evidence on clinical outcomes. Heffernan and Pilkington (2011) examined the evidence for the UK specifically, identifying high-fidelity versions of IPS as promising in increasing employment over 6-18 months, but noting significant implementation barriers (as noted in above section).

Probyn et al (2021) examine supported employment in relation to mental health conditions other than severe mental health. Across 10 randomised controlled trials (913 participants), the authors found that supported employment was more effective than control interventions in improving competitive employment for several groups. These included individuals with affective disorders (RR 10.61), justice-involved individuals with mental disorders (RR 4.44), veterans with PTSD (RR 2.73), formerly incarcerated veterans (RR 2.17), people in methadone treatment (RR 11.5), veterans with spinal cord injuries at both 12 months (RR 2.46) and 24 months (RR 2.81), and young people not in employment, education, or training (RR 5.90). However, no significant benefits were found for workers with musculoskeletal injuries (RR 1.38), individuals with substance abuse (RR 1.85), or formerly homeless people with mental illness (RR 1.55). The findings suggest supported employment may benefit a broader range of populations beyond those

with severe mental illness. Standardising definitions of competitive employment and improving measurement of non-vocational outcomes could enhance future research.

Variations on IPS, beyond low-fidelity versions or application to other target conditions, also include models which seek to promote engagement with schooling. For example, Rosenhek et al (2017) and Humensky et al (2019) investigate supported employment and education (SEE) – offered similarly to IPS but encouraging participation in education among young adults with early psychosis – and identify potentially promising results. Rosenhek et al (2017) documents effects of SEE as part of a broader trial, and notes that the intervention achieves desired outcomes – i.e. encouraging school attendance, even in combination with other elements such as family psychotherapy. However, the study had significant challenges in relation to baseline imbalances; similarly, the study by Humensky et al uses existing routine data from an employment programme and has no controls. Both studies suggest that SEE-like interventions could benefit from further investigation.

The main gap in evidence surrounding both supported employment and IPS relates to concurrent measurement of both employment and mental health outcomes. Existing studies are limited in their measurement of mental health outcomes, for example not examining effects on symptoms, and instead largely focusing on risk of hospitalisation. While the latter is important, longer-term monitoring of effects on symptoms and quality of life is important for understanding the benefits of this intervention, or potential harms or unintended consequences. Implementing IPS also for younger adults is promising, including potentially also examining variation and/or combination with SEE interventions – but evidence on the latter is scarce. Further research should also consider how diverse types of economic interventions compare in relation to mental health outcomes – for example, comparing cash transfers with models such as IPS.

Relevance to PLE:

The voices of PLE directly informed intervention development. Interviewees noted that early studies in workplace participation and mental health documented how persons affected by psychosis and schizophrenia prioritised engaging in work as a key recovery outcome and as a result, supported employment models emerged. PLE engagement also appears critical in building the case for further scaling. One interviewee noted that beyond the evidence, testimonials by PLE and their inclusion in advocacy efforts in support of the intervention is crucial in mobilising political and financial support.

Hutchinson et al (2018) document some examples of the above with reference to the UK. The authors note that PLE helped build the case for why IPS models are preferred to other interventions. For example, service user feedback emphasised that the IPS employment specialists understood their experiences, treated them as individuals, and built trusting relationships. This was in contrast to traditional job centre services, where PLE felt misunderstood and disempowered. The authors note that PLE testimonies also helped shift organisational culture—where employment was seen not just as an outcome, but as a central component of recovery. Drawing on PLE testimonies (written and verbal), IPS specialists and team leaders worked to reframe employment support from being an optional extra to being core to mental health recovery, which resonated deeply with service users and staff alike. Core to this practice was the willingness of previous IPS clients becoming informal advocates themselves. Their testimonials and engagement helped legitimize IPS to clinicians and managers who were initially sceptical.

Engagement of PLE in both development and scaling of the intervention is clearly facilitated by the fact that supported employment primarily acts on economic activity – there is therefore widespread interest in drawing on PLE perspectives.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

IPS scaling clearly has substantive resource requirements. Hutchinson et al (2018) comment on the various staffing requirements – for example for team leads and employment specialists – and also the heavy time involvement needed to ensure that service redesign and coordination can be put in place to

support affected individuals. The authors note that despite the benefits of IPS and large support from decision-makers at local levels, several trusts in the UK did not further pursue implementation due to funding limitations at regional levels. A key facilitator to promoting IPS was the Implementing Recovery through Organisational Change (ImROC) initiative which prompted local trusts to include supported employment initiatives and adopt a more psychosocial approach to support.

Bond's 2023 cost-effectiveness brief on IPS reviewed 10 economic analyses conducted across diverse geographic contexts: six from the United States, and one each from the UK, Canada, Europe, and Switzerland. The direct costs of IPS services primarily encompass expenses associated with IPS teams, including staffing and supervision, with annual per-client costs in the U.S. ranging from \$4,000 to \$7,500 (averaging \$5,956). These figures exclude mental health treatment, case management, housing, and other non-vocational services. Regarding cost-effectiveness, six of the studies found that total costs for IPS groups were lower than control groups, while two studies showed higher costs. However, the majority of studies had short follow-up periods, up to 2 years. Long-term studies (5+ years) are needed given that current existing evidence suggests that benefits from IPS may persist and even increase over time. Bond notes that many decision-makers consider IPS a cost-effective intervention for improving employment outcomes for people with mental health conditions, with implementation decisions ultimately resting on the willingness and ability to pay for these services. However, existing resource envelopes are too restricted to allow for scaling.

Further, it is unclear whether the general public would be in favour of scaling models such as IPS. In interviews, two main challenges were noted. First, scaling of IPS in conditions of limited resources may mean disinvestment from other areas (e.g. there may be reductions in other supports such as cash transfers). Second, there are still high levels of stigma against people suffering from severe mental illness; this also extends to their inclusion in workplaces. How to encourage adoption of models such as IPS thus also critically relies on destigmatisation initiatives and social support.

Evidence on cost-effectiveness and costs is scarce beyond the above and it is clear that it could be expanded. Economic evaluations which adopt a societal perspective and long-term time horizon, and are conducted across diverse economic contexts are needed to inform investment cases.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Drake and Bond (2023) note that IPS is now scaled to more than 20 countries, predominantly high-income settings. The intervention is clearly applicable across a variety of economic contexts as demonstrated by Modini et al (2016). However, there are expected barriers to scalability of this intervention to low-resource settings and/or settings with specific legal and disability contexts.

Mavindidze, Nhunzi and van Niekerk (2023) review the evidence on supported employment interventions across LMICs and identifies 8 studies of highly diverse methods across Colombia, Costa Rica, Peru, South Africa, China, and India. The authors identify found that supported employment interventions yield several positive mental health benefits, including enhanced social functioning and a better quality of life. Employment was linked to reduced symptom severity for mental disorders such as schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and depressive disorders, and there were reports of increased self-efficacy and confidence among participants. However, the review also identified notable limitations. Research in this area has primarily focused on vocational outcomes, with studies focusing on an inconsistent set of mental health measures; long-term follow-up data is also usually lacking. Additionally, contextual challenges such as stigma and limited access to comprehensive mental health services in LMICs may have influenced the results.

Interviewees supported the potential for IPS to be used across a diversity of settings but noted that there would be significant challenges in adaptation to low-resource contexts. For example, high levels of unemployment and informal work make it very difficult to implement IPS; the general view that IPS requires high-fidelity implementation also make it difficult to engage with developers on adaptations. One

interviewee noted however that the principles of IPS could be adapted – e.g. using informal worker groups or cooperatives, or even community groups, and pairing these with existing community-based supports and health / social workers to implement an IPS like model. Support for the development and incubation of such models and establishment of learning communities (which are an acknowledged facilitator elsewhere) is needed to catalyse advancement.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

IPS clearly acts on a social determinant of health and helps reduce inequity by enabling persons with severe mental illness to participate in work. The evidence focuses predominantly on participation outcomes, but as noted in the Efficacy and Effectiveness section, studies suggest that impacts persist over time and that wages are comparable if not higher than those of control groups.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

There are significant barriers which affect IPS and supported employment adoption across settings with respect to assisting treatment for psychosis and severe mental illness, as well as depression and anxiety. First, the evidence base must document both short and long-term clinical effects and must also include costing of implementation. Cost-effectiveness studies across diverse economic contexts are needed to better understand the value for money of the intervention, specifically also when considering IPS compared to other types of psychological interventions which ultimately aim to affect entry into work. Evidence in other populations -specifically depression and anxiety – is also needed. Second, variations across different populations and settings (different countries, service contexts, or providers) further suggest that system-level barriers—like funding, policy differences, or local resource limitations—can impede IPS scaling. Third, difficulties in offering integrated models like IPS must also be noted. Professional protectionism, stigma, resistance to change were mentioned both by interviewees as well as in literature around IPS.

Key facilitators to IPS’s scaling include the intervention being firmly grounded in lived experience – by directly responding to a need, IPS ensures immediate buy-in and willingness from PLE and service providers to engage. Active involvement of both clinicians and employment specialists—and the engagement of individuals with lived experience—proves vital in overcoming stigma and operational hurdles. Availability of key evidence on vocational effects has been important in creating a persuasive case for scaling.

One key lesson that emerges relates how IPS has evolved over time due to robust hybrid research. Developers of the model prioritised both implementation and effectiveness measurements and were able to secure funding for robust and repeated studies into IPS, which led to continued refinement of the intervention. Explicitly identifying evidence-based principles of actions given this evidence, and manualising the intervention, has ensured wider access and also the development of champions of IPS within the space. There are multiple learning communities which can now assist others with IPS adaptation and implementation, and this has considerably precipitated scaling.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- Expand the Evidence Base:
 - There are two types of research investments that are needed. First, it is important to invest in research that examines the effectiveness of IPS across diverse economic contexts, incorporates longer-term outcomes, and specifically evaluates its impact on mental health symptoms. Costing and cost-effectiveness studies should accompany the above developments.
 - Second, research is needed to identify the factors that facilitate the adoption of interventions like IPS. While IPS has demonstrated consistent benefits across high-income settings, it is

equally important to understand the conditions under which it can be effectively adopted at regional or national levels. This includes examining strategies that support scale-up—such as models of public and lived experience (PLE) engagement or the role of collaborative practice communities. Research should also explore public preferences for investment and the trade-offs faced by decision-makers. For instance, adopting IPS at scale may require reallocating existing resources, making approaches like programme budgeting and marginal analysis valuable tools for guiding such decisions.

- **Develop Adapted Models:** Create and refine prototype models for delivering IPS-like interventions in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Increase investment in research to build evidence on the effectiveness of these models. Facilitate dialogue between experts and individuals with lived experience (PLE) to co-develop these models and leverage learning communities for knowledge sharing and ensure follow-up research to assess and refine interventions.

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